

How to Find and Access Data in Europe

A practical introduction

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Overview

- ◇ Data types and sources
- ◇ Identify what you need
- ◇ Searching data archives
- ◇ Evaluating data: quality and usefulness
- ◇ Accessing data

CESSDA Training Working Group (2017)

Data types and sources

Activity 1

Your knowledge and experience of the data landscape

- ◇ Introduce yourself
- ◇ Tell us about your research work (current, future, past)
- ◇ Did you use or you intend to use available data for your work? Tell us about it.

Types of data

Thinking about the types of data available can help you work out what you need and how to find it.

Quantitative and Qualitative

Types of data: level of analysis

Macro data

- Aggregate
 - about populations, groups, regions and countries constructed by combining information on lower level units (e.g. unemployment rate, fertility)
- System level
 - characteristics of higher-level units such as the state or the political system e.g. electoral system (PR or single-member districts) and member of EU

Meso data

- data on collective and cooperative actors such as commercial companies, organizations or political parties

Microdata

- data from individual units (often people or households) often from surveys, a census and administrative records

Types of data: time

Cross-sectional

- one-point of time (a snap shot)
- usually information on multiple cases and variables

Repeated cross sectional

- cross-sectional surveys repeated with new samples
- data from the different samples allows analysis of trends

Time series

- series of data points in time order (often equally spaced in time)
- aggregate macro data are often time-series data.
- time points may come from sample surveys e.g. unemployment from labour force surveys

Longitudinal

- follow the same units over time e.g. household panel studies collect information from a sample of households in regular 'waves'

Sources of data

There are many sources of data.

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European social science data archives

YHTEISKUNTATIETEELLINEN
TIETOARKISTO
FINLANDS
SAMHÄLLSVETENSKAPLIGA
DATAARKIV
FINNISH SOCIAL
SCIENCE DATA ARCHIVE

UK Data Service

Data collections include:

- ◊ variation between archives
- ◊ quantitative data - major source of individual level data
- ◊ qualitative
- ◊ outputs of
 - ◊ major academic projects
 - ◊ government/policy
 - ◊ small research teams
 - ◊ individual researchers
- ◊ recent and less recent data
- ◊ different languages

Data Archiving and Networked Services
DANS

SND Swedish National Data Service

NSD NORWEGIAN CENTRE FOR RESEARCH DATA

ČSDA

Czech Social Science Data Archive
Institute of Sociology

Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives

"enabling the research community to conduct high-quality research in the social science"

Key tasks:

- ◊ Developing standards and best practices around the management and archiving of social science data.
- ◊ Facilitating access to important data resources
- ◊ Work done by developing tools, training and co-ordinating network.
- ◊ [CESSDA data catalogue.](#)

Members

- » Austria
- » Belgium
- » Croatia
- » Czech Republic
- » Denmark
- » France
- » Finland
- » Germany
- » Greece
- » Hungary
- » Netherlands
- » North Macedonia
- » Norway
- » Portugal
- » Serbia
- » Slovakia
- » Slovenia
- » Sweden
- » Switzerland
- » UK

■ Members
■ Partners

National data services

Activities include:

- ◇ checking the quality of data and metadata,
- ◇ maintaining catalogues,
- ◇ managing access to data through appropriate licensing,
- ◇ obtaining data and
- ◇ training for both those creating and using data.

Open Access to research data

(European Commission)

Open access (OA) can be defined as the practice of providing on-line access to scientific information that is free of charge to the user and that is re-usable.

Open access to 'scientific information' refers to two main categories:

- ◊ **Peer-reviewed scientific publications** (primarily research articles published in academic journals)
- ◊ **Scientific research data: data underlying publications and/or other data** (such as curated but unpublished datasets or raw data)

AS OPEN AS POSSIBLE, AS CLOSED AS NECESSARY

HOW IT WORKS

 #openaccess
#opendata
#H2020

Open Access to research data

Importance of research infrastructures / data repositories

Source: EC

Horizon Europe

2021-2027

Reinforce openness

Open Science will become the modus operandi of Horizon Europe. It will go beyond the open access policy of Horizon 2020 and require open access to publications, data, and to research data management plans.

Slovenian Social Science Data Archives (ADP)

- ◇ Founded in 1997
- ◇ Slovenian national data repository for social sciences
- ◇ 600 social science surveys with data in a data catalogue + 150 with metadata
- ◇ Cca. 800 users registered in 2017 (90 % education, 10 % scientific/research purpose)
- ◇ 168 survey data used for detailed secondary-analysis in 2017

- ◇ Oldest data sets in the archive (public opinion polls) are from 1966
- ◇ Wide range of topics covered
- ◇ In most cases data relates only to Slovenia / few international
- ◇ Metadata in SI and EN, datafiles mostly in SI

The screenshot shows the homepage of the Slovenian Social Science Data Archives (ADP). The header includes the ADP logo, the name 'ARHIV DRUŽBOSLOVNIH PODATKOV', and the tagline 'Analiziraj podatke! Deli raziskavo! Prispevaj k znanosti!'. There are navigation links for 'UPORABI PODATKE', 'PREDAJ RAZISKAVO', 'USPOSOBI SE', and 'SPOZNAJ ADP'. A search bar is also present. The main content area is divided into sections: 'KAKO DO PODATKOV?' with icons for 'POIŠČI', 'REGISTRIRAJ SE', and 'ANALIZIRAJ'; 'KAKO PREDATI PODATKE?' with icons for 'EVIDENTIRAJ', 'PRIPRAVI', and 'PREDAJ'; 'BLOG' with a 'NOVICE' section; and 'IZPOSTAVLJAMO' with a featured article about 'Gradiva delavnice: Pravnih in etičnih vidikov ravnanja z raziskovalnimi podatki, 11. april, Ljubljana'. At the bottom, there are sections for 'ZADNJE OBJAVLJENE RAZISKAVE', 'AKTIVNOSTI ADP', and 'KONFERENCE IN DOGODKI'.

UK Data Service

Access to the UK's largest collection of social, economic and population data

Support for users with training and guidance.

[UK data service](https://www.ukdataservice.ac.uk/)

- ◇ major UK and cross-national surveys
- ◇ longitudinal studies (household panel and cohort studies)
- ◇ UK Census 1971-2011
- ◇ qualitative data collections
- ◇ research data in a researcher repository (Reshare)

Cross-national studies

International survey research programmes include many European countries

International Social Survey Programme (ISSP)

- ◇ annual programme (started in 1984)
- ◇ cross-national collaboration
- ◇ rotating thematic modules e.g.
 - ◇ Citizenship: 2004 and 2014
 - ◇ Work Orientations: 1989, 1997, 2005, 2015
 - ◇ Role of Government: 1985, 1990, 1996, 2006, 2016

Data Download

[Data Catalogue](#)

gesis

Leibniz-Institut
für Sozialwissenschaften

European Social Survey (ESS)

- ◊ A biennial cross-national survey (started in 2002)
- ◊ Highest methodological standard
- ◊ Freely available data for 36 countries (23 countries in 2016)

	R1 2002	R2 2004	R3 2006	R4 2008	R5 2010	R6 2012	R7 2014	R8 2016
Media and social trust	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
Politics	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
Subjective well-being...	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
Gender, Household	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
Socio demographics	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
Human values	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
Immigration	•						•	
Citizen involvement	•							
Health and care		•						
Economic morality		•						
Family work and well-being		•			•			

Probably most used / cited data. 125 T registered users, 89 T data downloads

Source: [ESS](#)

Topline Results issue 6 out now

Our report identifies rates of self-diagnosed physical and mental health conditions in 21 European nations.

More...

Social Inequalities in Health and their Determinants:
Topline Results from Round 7 of the European Social Survey

ESS Topline Results Series **6** Issue

Latest news

-
06/04/17

General Assembly meeting later this month
-
27/03/17

Madrid to host latest event
-
24/03/17

ESS presents at European conferences
-
13/03/17

Roger Jowell Memorial Lecture 2017

Data and Documentation

Data and documentation can be accessed by round (year), by theme or by country. Data are available for download and online analysis.

Methodological Research

The European Social Survey runs a programme of research to support and enhance the methodology that underpins the high standards it pursues in every aspect of survey design, data collection and archiving.

Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE)

- ◇ longitudinal study
- ◇ more than 140,000 individuals aged 50
- ◇ 27 European countries and Israel
- ◇ micro data on health, socio-economic status and social and family networks

A screenshot of the SHARE project website. The browser address bar shows "www.share-project.org". The website has a navigation bar with a "Select Country" dropdown menu. Below the navigation bar, there is a header section with the SHARE logo on the left, a map of Europe in the center, and the text "Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe" on the right. The main content area is divided into several sections: a left sidebar with a menu (Home, Organisation, Data Access, Data Documentation, Special Data Sets, SHARE Publications, Press & News, Contact), a central main content area with a "You are here: Home" breadcrumb, a search bar, and a "News" section with several articles (Wave 6 data released, Launch of the Executive Master's Programme, Rtrain, SHARE Newsletter No. 20), and a right sidebar with a "Newsletter" section and social media links (Twitter, Facebook). A large group photo of people is featured in the main content area, with the caption "SHARE Wave 7 Post-Pretest Meeting Vilnius, Lithuania 16-18 March, 2016".

Examples: Longitudinal studies

Household panel studies

following households over time and asking questions on a broad range of topics such as household composition, employment, earnings, health, social and political participation and life-satisfaction

The logo for the German Socio-Economic Panel (SOEP), featuring the letters 'SOEP' in a bold, sans-serif font. The 'S' and 'O' are red, and the 'E' and 'P' are blue.

- ◇ German Socio-Economic Panel (SOEP)
- ◇ Understanding society (and the British Household Panel Study)
- ◇ Swiss Household Panel

Schweizer Haushalt-Panel
Panel suisse de ménages
Swiss Household Panel

Five key data providing organizations

Eurostat – Statistics office of European Union

LIS - harmonised socio-economic micro datasets

OECD – key source of comparable statistical, economic and social data

World Bank - Free and open access to global development data

IMF - time series data on economic and financial indicators

Statistical office of the European Union

Provides national and sub-national data

- ◊ economy and finance, population and social conditions, industry, trade, agriculture and fisheries, transport, environment and energy and science, technology and innovation

Microdata

- ◊ e.g European Community Household Panel, European Union Labour Force Survey, European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions

Metadata for Official Statistics

MISSY (**Microdata Information System**) is an online service platform that provides structured metadata for official statistics. MISSY includes metadata at the study and variable level as well as reports and tools for data handling and analysis. All documentation in MISSY refers to microdata available for scientific purposes. MISSY currently documents the following official statistics microdata:

EU-Data

- [AES](#) (Adult Education Survey)
- [CIS](#) (Community Innovation Survey)
- [EU-LFS](#) (European Union Labour Force Survey)
- [EU-SILC](#) (European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions)
- [SES](#) (Structure of Earnings Survey)

National Data

- [MZ](#) (German microcensus)

Microcensus (DE)

EU-Data

AES

CIS

EU-LFS

EU-SILC

Browse ▲

2016 2015 2014 2013

2012 2011 2010 2009

2008 2007 2006 2005

Cross-sectional

Select Variable List

Original Order	Thematic Order

Matrix ▼

Setups

Materials ▼

Tools ▼

Study: EU-SILC 2016

- Titles ▼
- Abstract ▼
- Coverage ▼
- Notes ▼
- References ▼

Country Specific Information: EU-SILC 2016

AT	BE	BG	CY	CZ	DE	DK	EE	EL/GR	ES	FI	FR	HR
HU	LT	LV	NL	NO	PL	PT	RO	RS	SE	SI	SK	UK

SI - Slovenia

- National Reference ▼
- Target Sample Size ▼
- Available Data ▼
- Sampling Procedure ▼
- Panel Design ▼
- Data Collection ▼

Source: [MISSY](#)

Series and studies for SLOVENIA ×

- Census
- Central Population Register (CPR)
- Community Innovation Survey (CIS)
- European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions (EU-SILC)
- External Trade
- Final accounts
- Graduates in tertiary education
- Gross Fixed Capital Formation
- Household Budget Survey (HBS)
- Industrial production
- Labour Force Survey (LFS)
- Personal Income Tax
- Slovenian Business Register
- Statistical Register of Employment
- Student enrolment in tertiary education
- Time Use Survey (TUS)
- Unemployed workers
- Usage of information-communication technologies in enterprises
- Victimization Survey (VS)

Factsheet: Accreditation & Data Access Conditions for SLOVENIA

Contact

Name

Statistični urad Republike Slovenije (Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia, SORS)

Postal Address

Litostrojska cesta 54 SI-1000 Ljubljana (Slovenia)

Contact

info.stat@gov.si

Website

[\[click here\]](#)

Conditions

General Conditions

Microdata can be provided for research purposes to registered research institutions and registered researchers in both academia and government offices. "Registered" researchers have a national identifier. As a general rule, users submit applications for access that are assessed by a Confidentiality committee (internal to SORS); the latter prepares recommendations for SORS's board of directors, which makes the final decision.

Conditions for Non-Resident Researchers

Same as national researchers (though requests from non-registered researchers should be evaluated by the internal Confidentiality committee).

Source: [CIMES](#)

Series and studies for SLOVENIA	
	Census
	Central Population Register (CPR)
	Community Innovation Survey (CIS)
	European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions (EU-SILC)
	External Trade
	Final accounts
	Graduates in tertiary education
	Gross Fixed Capital Formation
	Household Budget Survey (HBS)
	Industrial production
	Labour Force Survey (LFS)
	Labour Force Survey - 1995
	Labour Force Survey - 1996
	Labour Force Survey - 1997
	Labour Force Survey - 1998
	Labour Force Survey - 1999
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	Labour Force Survey - 2006
	Labour Force Survey - 2007
	Labour Force Survey - 2008
	Labour Force Survey - 2009

Study

Labour Force Survey - 2011

Original Title :

Anketa o delovni sili - 2011

Original Alternative Title :

ADS - 2011

English Alternative Title:

LFS - 2011

Producer : SORS.

Abstract :

Slovenian Labour Force Survey 2011 is a Slovenian research with a tradition. The LFS measures the labour status and other characteristics of the population in a certain week of each quarter, by spreading the sample uniformly over all the weeks of the quarter. The survey provides data on size, structure and characteristics of active and inactive population. Data on personal income are added to the dataset (DURS register) – an average monthly income in either the whole year or a shorter period of time, if a person had worked for less than a year. Approximately 19.750 individuals are selected to the sample in each quarter. Non-anonymised version of LFS microdata is available to researchers, onsite or by remote access. The survey was conducted as one of the surveys of the Eurostat Labour Force Survey which includes data from 27 Member States of the European Union, four Candidate Countries and two EFTA countries (Norway and Switzerland). Comparability through time and space is possible as Eurostat distributes Labour Force Survey data of other participating countries.

Keywords :

LABOUR AND EMPLOYMENT, SOCIAL STRATIFICATION AND GROUPINGS

Geographic coverage : Slovenia.

Universe :

The target population is the jure population, which includes persons that are mainly living in the territory of Republic of Slovenia, regardless of their nationality. Only the population, is living in individual households, is covered by the survey. Institutionalized people are not considered as a part of the jure population. Those who live in institutions (soldiers, hospitalized, imprisoned etc.) for more than 12 months, including students who don't live at home and Slovenian citizens who live abroad permanently or temporarily, are not covered by the survey.

Sampling Procedure :

The Labour Force Survey is based on the sample taken from the Central Population Register. It is a rotating panel carried out continuously throughout the whole year. The sampling method is stratified systematic random sampling of addresses. All members of the household at the selected address are included in the sample. That means that there are approximately 16 150 individuals included in each

CIMES

Centralising and Integrating Metadata from European Statistics

Source: [CIMES](#)

Direct from project websites

Some research projects share research data through project websites

[Home](#) [About](#) [Data](#) [People](#) [Publications](#) [Working Paper Series](#) [FAQs](#) [Links](#)

<http://cwed2.org/>

WELCOME

The Comparative Welfare Entitlements Dataset (CWED) contains information about the structure and generosity of social insurance benefits in 33 countries around the world. Since September 2017, an updated version of CWED 2 containing a total of **eight household types** is available. The data contained here are an updated and extended version of CWED 1, which has been available since 2004.

Principal Investigators:
Lyle Scruggs
Kati Kuitto
Detlef Jahn

This web site allows you to download customized portions of the CWED 2 data, browse the Working Paper Series or access documentary material.

[Download CWED 2 data here](#)

NEWS

June 22, 2017

Updated list of scientific works and papers is available

More than 200 peer-reviewed scientific works are using CWED2 data. You can access an updated of all books, papers, and chapters in edited volumes using our dataset [here](#).

June 09, 2017

Forthcoming publications from CWED members

Data repositories

Digital archives collecting, preserving and displaying datasets, related documentation and metadata.

Types of repository

domain-specific
trusted repositories
(e.g. CESSDA
archives) - focus on
high-quality data with
a potential for reuse

institutional
research data
repositories e.g.
universities

general purpose
repositories e.g.
Zenodo, Figshare,
Harvard
Dataverse

A registry of research data repositories

Search

- ◇ by subject, content type and country
- ◇ for data archives with a certificate (a trusted repository), open access or for data sets that have a persistent identifier

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Identify what you need

Four ways we can use archived data

1 New analysis: one or multiple data sources e.g. combine micro and macro, just secondary data or secondary data combined with primary data

2 Replication

3 Use of study design/methodology (e.g. data collection tools (interview schedules & survey questions) or sampling strategies)

4 Teaching : Subject-based or research methods,
Datasets made for training purposes – e.g. easySHARE

Identifying data needs

Research Question

- What is the ideal dataset for addressing this question?
(Compromises needed in reality)

Key concepts

How to operationalise?

(concepts can be complex and difficult to measure)

- ◇ Key features
- ◇ Multidimensional
- ◇ Groups of people
- ◇ Dependent/independent variables

- ◇ What variables/multiple variables?
- ◇ Comparable/established measures (e.g. Schwarz Human Values)

Identifying data needs

- ◊ Who are you concerned with?
- ◊ e.g. people/adults/EU citizens, migrants, local authorities

- ◊ e.g. specific countries or regions,
- ◊ all EU countries or A10 countries (2004)

- ◊ As most recent as possible
- ◊ a specific period (e.g. 2008-2018)
- ◊ a long a period as possible
- ◊ data from people at multiple time points?

- ◊ individuals, households, regions or countries?

- ◊ Do you need representative (random) sample?
- ◊ Size (large sample for inferences about small groups)

Activity

Identify data needs

- ◆ Task: identify data needs - Evaluating data worksheet

Searching data archives

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Three types of search

- ◇ Search for data on a topic
- ◇ Search for a specific dataset
- ◇ Browse data collections by type or theme

Online catalogues – searching (browsing)

SND Swedish National Data Service

Search on site | På svenska

language

FIND AND ORDER DATA DATA MANAGEMENT DESCRIBE AND DEPOSIT DATA SND EVENTS ABOUT US

Order data SND Online Analysis Collections Data in Focus International data Questions & variables Accessibility levels

Home / Find and order data

Site map

Find and order data

Filter	
Kind of data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Subject	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Principal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Funding agency	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Availability status	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Series	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Geographic location	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

political attitudes

SEARCH

247 hits

Previous 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 .. 24 25 Next

[Socio-political attitudes 1975](#)

Stockholm University

The central aim of the study is looking at various aspects of political perception as a function of socio-political ideology. The politically perceived objects consists mainly of political parties, party-leaders and c...

▪ Bo Ekehammar, Stockholm University, Department of Psychology

Published: 1987

1C

[Socio-political attitudes 1979](#)

Stockholm University

The aim of the study is basically the same as in Socio-Political Attitudes 1975. In the

Filter/sort

ADP - SOCIAL SCIENCE DATA ARCHIVES

Analyze data! Deposit study! Promote science!

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USE DATA DEPOSIT STUDY LEARN ABOUT DISCOVER ADP

SEARCH

List of studies by:

- Study ID
- Series
- Study topics
- Depositors
- Year of Production
- Year of Publication
- Author
- International studies

Use data / ADP Catalogue

ADP CATALOGUE

Date of the last change of the catalog: 05.07.2018

List of studies by study's ID

Study ID	Study title, topic	Access
EUVET12	7 EU VET - Study on vocational education in seven european countries topic: EDUCATION, EDUCATION - vocational education, produced by: CDI	nesstor
EWCS05	European Working Conditions Survey 2005 topic: LABOUR AND EMPLOYMENT, LABOUR AND EMPLOYMENT - employment, produced by: EUROFOUND	nesstor
EWCS01	Working Conditions in European Union Candidate Countries, 2001 topic: LABOUR AND EMPLOYMENT, LABOUR AND EMPLOYMENT - employment, produced by: EUROFOUND	nesstor
FEMAKT16	Intersectionality and Feminist Activism, 2016: Student Feminist Societies in the United Kingdom topic: SOCIAL STRATIFICATION AND GROUPINGS, SOCIAL STRATIFICATION AND GROUPINGS - gender and gender roles, produced by: None	nesstor

Study Topics

- DEMOGRAPHY, POPULATION, VITAL STATISTICS AND CENSUSES
- [ECONOMICS](#)
- EDUCATION
- HEALTH
- HOUSING AND LAND USE PLANNING
- INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION
- LABOUR AND EMPLOYMENT
- LAW, CRIME AND LEGAL SYSTEMS
- NATURAL ENVIRONMENT
- Not categorized
- OTHER
- POLITICS
- PSYCHOLOGY
- SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY
- SOCIAL STRATIFICATION AND GROUPINGS
- SOCIAL WELFARE POLICY AND SYSTEMS
- SOCIETY AND CULTURE
- TRADE, INDUSTRY AND MARKETS
- TRANSPORT, TRAVEL AND MOBILITY

Economic Morality (ESS2 2004)

Data/Variables - Round 2 (2004)

- ❶ Citizens should spend some free time helping others
- ❶ Society better off if everyone looked after themselves
- ❶ Citizens should not cheat on taxes
- ❶ Trust plumber/builder/mechanic/other repairer deal honestly with you
- ❶ Trust financial companies/bank/insurers deal honestly with you
- ❶ Trust public officials deal honestly with you
- ❶ Plumber/builder/mechanic/repairer overcharged you, how often last 5 years
- ❶ You were sold food packed to conceal worse bits, how often last 5 years
- ❶ Bank/insurance company failed to offer best deal, how often last 5 years
- ❶ You were sold things second-hand that proved faulty, how often last 5 years
- ❶ Public official asked favour/bribe for service, how often last 5 years
- ❶ How worried are you of being treated dishonestly
- ❶ Someone paying cash without receipt to avoid VAT or tax, how wrong

Source: [ESS](#)

Documentation often extensive

ESS Rounds

[ESS Round 8 \(2016\)](#)

[ESS Round 7 \(2014\)](#)

[ESS Round 6 \(2012\)](#)

[ESS Round 5 \(2010\)](#)

[ESS Round 4 \(2008\)](#)

[ESS Round 3 \(2006\)](#)

[ESS Round 2 \(2004\)](#)

[ESS Round 1 \(2002\)](#)

ESS8 - 2016 Data Download

The ESS8-2016 Edition 1.1 was released on 9th of April 2018. Please see [Version notes](#) for complete information.

Users are obliged to read the [ESS conditions of use](#). Please see [Deviations in data](#) for an overview of errors or deviations in different countries.

**ESS8 - integrated file
Edition 1.1**

Integrated files and documents

[ESS8 - integrated file, edition 1.1](#)

[ESS8 - data from Interviewer's questionnaire, edition 1.0](#)

[ESS8 - test data \(MTMM\), edition 1.0](#)

[ESS8 - data from Contact forms, edition 2.0](#)

[ESS8 - data from Media claims, edition 1.0](#)

[Guide to weighting of ESS data](#)

[FAQ: Combining data files, Renaming variables, Other data formats.](#)

[Fieldwork Summary and Deviations](#)

Survey Documentation

[ESS8 Data Documentation Report ed. 1.0](#)

[ESS8 Appendix A1 Education ed. 1.0](#)

[ESS8 Appendix A2 Income ed. 1.0](#)

[ESS8 Appendix A3 Political Parties ed. 1.0](#)

[ESS8 Appendix A4 Legal Marital and Relationship Status ed. 1.0](#)

[ESS8 Appendix A5 Population Statistics ed. 1.0](#)

[ESS8 Appendix A6 Classifications and Coding Standards ed. 1.0](#)

[ESS8 Appendix A7 Variables and Questions ed. 1.0](#)

ESS Findings

Findings from the European Social Survey are available in a number of publications.

[>>](#)

ESS Data Alerts

[ESS8 Swedish data removed - 09/04/18](#)

[ESS7 Error in INWMME and INWYYE for Netherlands - 12/02/18](#)

[ESS8 Error in INWMMS and INWYYS for Netherlands - 24/01/18](#)

[ESS8 Second edition \(2.0\) of Contact form data - 15/12/17](#)

Questions?

Questions regarding data or documentation, please contact

essdatasupport@nsd.no

Integrated File – Download

[Download ESS Round 8 \(2016\)](#)

[Download ESS Round 7 \(2014\)](#)

[Download ESS Round 6 \(2012\)](#)

[Download ESS Round 5 \(2010\)](#)

[Download ESS Round 4 \(2008\)](#)

[Download ESS Round 3 \(2006\)](#)

[Download ESS Round 2 \(2004\)](#)

NESSTAR for online browsing and analysis

The screenshot displays the ESS DATA interface. The top header includes the European Social Survey logo, the text 'ESS DATA', and 'NORWEGIAN SOCIAL SCIENCE DATA SERVICES (NSD)'. Below the header is a navigation bar with tabs for 'DESCRIPTION', 'TABULATION', and 'ANALYSIS'. The left sidebar contains a tree view with categories: 'ESS' (listing rounds from 2002 to 2016), 'Metadata' (including 'Study Description' and 'Data Access'), and 'Variable Description' (listing various topics like 'Country', 'Weights', 'Media and social trust', etc.). The main content area shows the 'DESCRIPTION' tab selected, displaying the title 'European Social Survey (2017). ESS Round 8 (2016/2017) Technical Report. London: ESS ERIC'. Below this, there are sections for 'List of Keywords' (including Trust, politics, social values, etc.) and 'Topic Classification' (including Social trust, political interest and participation, etc.). At the bottom, a 'Country' section lists participating nations.

- online data browsing and analysis
- download tables, graphs, data files and study descriptions
- main catalogue or additional tool
- help pages [? at top]

Frequency distribution of one variable

Variable mnactic: Main activity, last 7 days. All respondents. Post coded

LITERAL QUESTION

F17c2. POST CODE: MAIN ACTIVITY

Values Categories

1	Paid work
2	Education
3	Unemployed, looking for job
4	Unemployed, not looking for job
5	Permanently sick or disabled
6	Retired
7	Community or military service
8	Housework, looking after children, other
9	Other
66	Not applicable
77	Refusal
88	Don't know
99	No answer

	Code	Frequency	% of all	% of valid
Main activity, last 7 days. All respondents. Post coded				
Paid work	1	25,760	47.1	47.6
Education	2	4,704	8.6	8.7
Unemployed, looking for job	3	2,978	5.4	5.5
Unemployed, not looking for job	4	1,155	2.1	2.1
Permanently sick or disabled	5	1,291	2.4	2.4
Retired	6	12,819	23.4	23.7
Community or military service	7	90	0.2	0.2
Housework, looking after children, others	8	4,796	8.8	8.9
Other	9	520	1.0	1.0
Refusal	77	39	0.1	-
Don't know	88	105	0.2	-
No answer	99	416	0.8	-
Total		54,673	100.0	100.0

SUMMARY STATISTICS

This variable is numeric

Source: ESS; Dataset: ESS6-2012, ed.2.4

Crosstabs – frequency distribution of two variables

Socio-demographics

- Main activity last 7 days
- Main activity, last 7 days. All respondents. Post coded
- Interviewer code, respondent in paid work
- Control paid work last 7 days
- Ever had a paid job
- Year last in paid job
- Employment relation
- Number of employees respondent has/had
- Employment contract unlimited or limited duration

- Add to row
- Add to column
- Use as filter
- Add as measure

DESCRIPTION	TABULATION	ANALYSIS
-------------	------------	----------

Dataset: ESS6-2012, ed.2.1

	Choose 'Add to column' to place the variable here.
Choose 'Add to row' to place the variable here.	To populate this table you need to select a variable from the browse list, click on it and then add it to row, column or layers, or use it as a measure variable.

Politics

- Placement on left right scale
- How satisfied with life as a whole
- How satisfied with present state
- How satisfied with the national
- How satisfied with the way dem
- State of education in country ne
- State of health services in coun
- Government should reduce differences in income levels

- Add to row
- Add to column
- Use as filter
- Add as measure

Comparing **life satisfaction measures** of two groups – the unemployed people looking for work versus people in paid work. Calculate the means for the two groups across Europe.

- Main activity last 7 days
- Main activity, last 7 days. All respondents. Post coded
- Interviewer code, respondent in paid work
- Control paid work last 7 days
- Ever had a paid job
- Year last in paid job
- Employment relation
- Number of employees respondent has/had

- Add to row
- Add to column
- Use as filter
- Add as measure

- Placement on left right scale
- How satisfied with life as a whole
- How satisfied with present state
- How satisfied with the national government
- How satisfied with the way democracy works
- State of education in country now
- State of health services in country now
- Government should reduce differences in income levels
- Gays and lesbians free to live life as they wish

- Add to row
- Add to column
- Use as filter
- Add as measure

B20. All things considered, how satisfied are you with your life as a whole nowadays?

	Median	Average	Minimum	Maximum	Standard deviation	Sum	Count
Main activity, last 7 days. All respondents. Post coded							
Paid work	7.5	7.0	0.0	10.0	2.2	179,423.0	25,653
Education	8.0	7.7	0.0	10.0	1.9	35,885.0	4,676
Unemployed, looking for job	5.6	5.4	0.0	10.0	2.7	16,028.0	2,956
Unemployed, not looking for job	5.7	5.6	0.0	10.0	2.7	6,347.0	1,139
Permanently sick or disabled	5.6	5.5	0.0	10.0	2.8	7,037.0	1,278
Retired	7.0	6.5	0.0	10.0	2.5	83,123.0	12,725
Community or military service	7.6	6.9	0.0	10.0	2.6	618.0	90
Housework, looking after children, others	7.2	6.6	0.0	10.0	2.6	31,469.0	4,767
Other	7.6	7.0	0.0	10.0	2.4	3,599.0	517
Total	7.30	6.76	0.00	10.00	2.40	363,529.00	53,801

Source: ESS; Dataset: ESS6-2012, ed.2.4

Finding data

nesstar aesis

Please click on in the left t

ADVANCED SEARCH

Advanced Search - Google Chrome
https://zacat.gesis.org/webview/velocity?mode=searchview&searchtype=advanced&&

Advanced Search

Search criteria:

Variable + -

Search for: datasets variables

SEARCH

- Study Description
- Study Description
- Bibliographic Citation
 - Title Statement
 - Full Title
 - Identification Number
- Responsibility Statement
- Authoring Entity
- Production Statement
 - Producer
 - Copyright
 - Funding Agency/Sponsor
- Distributor Statement
 - Data Distributor
 - Abbreviation
 - Depositor
- Study Scope
- Subject Information
 - List of Keywords
 - Topic Classification
- Abstract

- EVS 2008: Belgium
- EVS 2008: Greece
- EVS 2008: Integrated Dataset
- EVS 2008: Estonia
- EVS 2008: Portugal
- EVS 2008: Lithuania
 - describe your state of health these days (Q4) [Open in context]
 - do you belong to: voluntary health organisations (Q5aN) [Open in context]
 - how much confidence in: health care system (Q63M) [Open in context]
 - do you work unpaid for: voluntary health organisations (Q5bN) [Open in context]
 - kind of job respondent - ISCO88 code (Q112) [Open in context]
 - kind of job spouse/partner - ISCO88 code (Q118) [Open in context]
 - kind of job father/mother - ISCO88 code (Q129a) [Open in context]
- EVS 2008: Turkey
- EVS 2008: Azerbaijan
- International Social Survey Programme: Social Inequality

ZA4768: EVS 2008: Lithuania

[ZA4768 Datafiles and Documentation download](#) (via data catalogue)

Variable v9: describe your state of health these days (Q4)

LITERAL QUESTION

Q4

<SHOW CARD 4>

All in all, how would you describe your state of health these days? Would you say it is

- 5 other missing
- 4 question not asked
- 3 nap
- 2 na
- 1 dk
- 1 very good
- 2 good
- 3 fair
- 4 poor
- 5 very poor

CESSDA data catalogue

The screenshot shows the CESSDA Data Catalogue website. The browser address bar displays 'https://datacatalogue-dev.cessda.eu'. The page header includes the CESSDA logo and the text 'DC Data Catalogue'. A search bar contains the text 'Find Social and Economic Research Data'. Below the search bar, it indicates '7163 results found in 20ms'. The page features a sidebar with filters for Topic, Country, Publisher, and Language of data files. The main content area shows search results, including a dropdown menu for 'Sort by' with options: Relevance (selected), Title (ascending), Title (descending), Date of collection (ascending), and Date of collection (descending). The first result is 'National Opinion Polls National Political Surveys; 2-7 July 1974' by NOP Market Research Limited. The second result is 'Disability Follow-Up to the 1996/97 Family Resources Survey' by the Department of Social Security, Social Research Branch.

Search data collection of
all CESSDA members

<https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/>

Finding data in practice

Searching can be hard

- Too many results
- No results
- Results not relevant

Evaluate search terms

- How well do they relate to your data needs?
- Spelling/language
- “Exact terms”, Boolean Logic (AND OR) – check how search tool works

Sort, filter, advance search

ELSST

Search for
concepts

ELSST covers the core
social science disciplines

Enter your search term and select
a language to browse ELSST

elsst.ukdataservice.ac.uk

Multilingual thesaurus of social science concepts.

Hierarchical and non-hierarchical relationships between concepts.

Use to:

- ◊ broaden or narrow a search
- ◊ find terms used to index data in other languages

In future, ELSST will be used more widely to index data & embedded within search tool.

Activity

Searching for data

Task

Search for data using a data catalogue

- Any national data service
- See CESSDA for links:
www.cessda.eu/Consortium

Evaluating data: quality and usefulness

Metadata and documentation

Metadata ("data about data")

- descriptors that facilitate cataloguing data and data discovery.

Documentation

- user guides, survey questionnaires, interview schedules and fieldwork notes

- ◊ Catalogue records (with links to documentation)
- ◊ Quality can vary
- ◊ Efforts to improve data documentation
- ◊ Check for helpdesks/training

What to look for when assessing quality?

Metadata ("data about data"):

- ◊ Why the data was created?
- ◊ What the dataset contains?
- ◊ How data was collected?
- ◊ Who collected the data and when?
- ◊ How was the data processed?
- ◊ Any manipulations done to the data?
- ◊ What quality assurance procedures were used?

But is it useful?

Compare:

- ◊ key concepts
- ◊ population
- ◊ geographical area
- ◊ time period
- ◊ units of analysis
- ◊ study/sample design

Accessing data

Now finally, I've found some great data, how to I get it?

- ◆ Licenses
- ◆ Access process
- ◆ Getting started

Data access arrangements 1

Open data

any user, no registering (acknowledge source)

Registration

- ◊ often with institutional user name and password
- ◊ may wait for user name or password
- ◊ register use of data

Terms and conditions

- ◊ not trying to identify individuals, households or organisations
- ◊ not distributing data to others
- ◊ “data is for non-commercial use only” or for “use in research or teaching” only.

Download

from catalogue (but sometimes complete a request form)

Data access arrangements 2

- ◊ Sometimes permission from the data owners required (= a additional stage)
- ◊ Sensitive or confidential data = more strict (and lengthy) process
- ◊ Some services operate a dedicated safe room or safe access service
- ◊ Access by users outside the country can be prohibited for confidential data
- ◊ Free (except for commercial use and supplementary services)

If you are unsure, ask the relevant data service for help.

And finally...remember to cite data

Why?

- It gives credit the data creators
- It makes data easier to find

How?

- Give enough information to locate the exact version of the data
- Look for recommended citation
- Use persistent identifiers (Digital Object Identifier - DOI)

CESSDA Training Working Group (2017)

Citation requirements

The Core Scientific Team of the ESS requests that references to ESS data and the Data Documentation Reports should use the form of words listed below.

To ensure that such source attributions are captured for social science bibliographic utilities, citations must appear in the footnotes or in the reference section of publications.

Citation of data

- ESS Round 8: European Social Survey Round 8 Data (2016). Data file edition 1.0. NSD - Norwegian Centre for Research Data, Norway - Data Archive and distributor of ESS data for ESS ERIC.
- ESS Round 7: European Social Survey Round 7 Data (2014). Data file edition 2.1. NSD - Norwegian Centre for Research Data, Norway - Data Archive and distributor of ESS data for ESS ERIC.
- ESS Round 6: European Social Survey Round 6 Data (2012). Data file edition 2.3. NSD - Norwegian Centre for Research Data, Norway - Data Archive and distributor of ESS data for ESS ERIC.
- ESS Round 5: European Social Survey Round 5 Data (2010). Data file edition 3.3. NSD - Norwegian Centre for Research Data, Norway - Data Archive and distributor of ESS data for ESS ERIC.
- ESS Round 4: European Social Survey Round 4 Data (2008). Data file edition 4.4. NSD - Norwegian Centre for Research Data, Norway - Data Archive and distributor of ESS data for ESS ERIC.
- ESS Round 3: European Social Survey Round 3 Data (2006). Data file edition 3.6. NSD - Norwegian Centre for Research Data, Norway - Data Archive and distributor of ESS data for ESS ERIC.
- ESS Round 2: European Social Survey Round 2 Data (2004). Data file edition 3.5. NSD - Norwegian Centre for Research Data, Norway - Data Archive and distributor of ESS data for ESS ERIC.
- ESS Round 1: European Social Survey Round 1 Data (2002). Data file edition 6.5. NSD - Norwegian Centre for Research Data, Norway - Data Archive and distributor of ESS data for ESS ERIC.

Citation of documentation

- ESS Round 8: European Social Survey (2017): ESS-8 2016 Documentation Report. Edition 1.0. Bergen, European Social Survey Data Archive, NSD - Norwegian Centre for Research Data for ESS ERIC.

are available in a number of publications.

>>

ESS Data Alerts

ESS8 Swedish data removed - 09/04/18

ESS7 Error in INWMME and INWYYE for Netherlands - 12/02/18

ESS8 Error in INWMMS and INWYYS for Netherlands - 24/01/18

ESS8 Second edition (2.0) of Contact form data - 15/12/17

Questions?

Questions regarding data or documentation, please contact essdatasupport@nsd.no

Integrated File – Download

[Download ESS Round 8 \(2016\)](#)

[Download ESS Round 7 \(2014\)](#)

[Download ESS Round 6 \(2012\)](#)

[Download ESS Round 5 \(2010\)](#)

[Download ESS Round 4 \(2008\)](#)

[Download ESS Round 3 \(2006\)](#)

[Download ESS Round 2 \(2004\)](#)

[Download ESS Round 1 \(2002\)](#)

Online Analysis

[Open ESS Round 8 \(2016\)](#)

[Open ESS Round 7 \(2014\)](#)

[Open ESS Round 6 \(2012\)](#)

[Open ESS Round 5 \(2010\)](#)

[Open ESS Round 4 \(2008\)](#)

ELEMENTS OF DATA CITATION

- **Author:** Name(s) of each individual or organizational entity responsible for the creation of the dataset.
- **Date of Publication:** Year the dataset was published or disseminated.
- **Title:** Complete title of the dataset, including the edition or version number, if applicable.
- **Publisher and/or Distributor:** Organizational entity that makes the dataset available by archiving, producing, publishing, and/or distributing the dataset.
- **Electronic Location or Identifier:** Web address or unique, persistent, global identifier used to locate the dataset (such as a DOI). Append the date retrieved if the title and locator are not specific to the exact instance of the data you used.

These are the minimum elements required for dataset identification and retrieval. Fewer or additional elements may be requested by author guidelines or style manuals. Be sure to include as many elements as needed to precisely identify the dataset you have used.

Source: [IASSIST – Quick guide to Data Citation](#)

ISSP Research Group (2017): International Social Survey Programme: Work Orientations IV - ISSP 2015. GESIS Data Archive, Cologne. ZA6770 Data file Version 2.1.0, doi:10.4232/1.12848

Hafner-Fink, M. and Malešič, M. (2016). Slovenian Public Opinion 2015: Work Orientation (ISSP 2015), Role of Government (ISSP 2016), Mirror of public opinion and National Security Survey [Data file]. Ljubljana: University of Ljubljana, Social Science Data Archives. ADP – IDNO: SJM15. https://doi.org/10.17898/ADP_SJM15_V1

Data Management Expert Guide

This guide is designed by European experts to help social science researchers make their research data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR).

You will be guided by different European experts who are - on a daily basis - busy ensuring long-term access to valuable social science datasets, available for discovery and reuse at one of the [CESSDA social science data archives](#).

Search this guide

Search

Data Management Expert Guide

- 1. Plan
- 2. Organise & Document
- 3. Process
- 4. Store
- 5. Protect
- 6. Archive & Publish
- 7. Discover

Target audience and mission

This guide is written for social science researchers who are in an early stage of practising research data management. With this guide, CESSDA wants to contribute to professionalism in data management and increase the value of research data.

Overview

If you follow the guide, you will travel through the research data lifecycle from planning, organising, documenting, processing, storing and protecting your data to sharing and publishing them. Taking the whole roundtrip will take you approximately 15 hours, however you can also hop on and off at any time.

www.cessda.eu/DMEG

More literature

- [Quick reference guide: Using administrative data for research](#)
- [Quick reference guide: Social media and research](#)
- [Guidelines on the use of social media data in survey research](#)

- [Data Management Expert Guide](#) (CESSDA)

Questions?

*Pictures from
CESSDA Training Working Group (2017). [CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide](#). Bergen, Norway: CESSDA ERIC.*